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IOV –INTERNET OF VEHICLES

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Abstract:

Internet of Things (IoT) is smartly changing various existing research areas into new themes including smart- phones, smart-health, smart-home, smart-industry and smart-transport. It is relying on the basis of ‘Smart-Transport’, Internet of Vehicles (IoV) is introducing as a new theme of research and development from Vehicular Adhoc Networks (VANETs). This paper presents and proposes a comprehensive framework of IoV with emphasis on layered architecture, protocol stack, network model, challenges and future aspects. Specifically it following the background on evolution of VANETs and motivation on IoV, as a result an overview of IoV is presented as a heterogeneous vehicular networks. The IoV includes mainly five types of vehicular communications; namely, Vehicle-to-Vehicle, Vehicle to-Roadside, Vehicle-to-Infrastructure of cellular networks, Vehicle-to-Personal devices and Vehicle-to-Sensors. A five layered architecture of IoV is proposed considering functionalities and representations of each layer present in it. A protocol stack for the layered architecture is structured considering management, operational and security planes. Now a days, A network model of IoV is proposed based on the three network elements including cloud, connection and client. The benefits of the design and development of IoV are improved by performing a qualitative comparison between IoV and VANETs. Finally, the challenges ahead for realizing IoV are discussed and future aspects of IoV are envisioned.

Keywords: ZIGBEE, GSM, BLUETOOTH, ACCELEROMETER

INTRODUCTION

The concept of a universal network framework that including all the existing heterogeneous networks is being strongly experienced and shaped now a days due to the highly growing number of things; e.g., vehicles on road, smartphones on the hands of people, laptops and tablets in offices, tvs and music systems in homes and other sensor enabled device in our daily life. This global network of things is nothing but a future internet communication which is being shaped as internet of things (IoT) among researchers and practitioners in academia and industries. In IoT, intelligent interfaces are utilized for seamlessly integration of heterogeneous communication networks. Interoperability among heterogeneous devices is one of the main goals of IoT . IoT is revolutionizing many new research and development areas. IoT is integrating smartness into the existing areas; e.g., smart-phones,smart-health, smart-home, smart-energy, smart industry and smart transport.

Internet of vehicle (IoV) is one of the revolutions mobilized by IoT, Internet Of Vehicles. IoV is based from vehicular adhoc networks (vanets) to achieve and develop the vision of ‘from smartphone to smartcar’. The main aim of conventional vanets was to improve traffic safety and efficiency using real time communication among advanced wireless access technology enabled vehicles with or without the help of road side units .In spite of having huge potential to address safety and efficiency issues of traffic with lower operational and performance cost, vanets has not been able to attract commercial interest. The commercialization problem of vanets includes the issues related to pure adhoc network architecture, unreliable internet service, incompatibility with personal devises, unavailability of cloud computing, lower accuracy of the services, and cooperative operational dependency of the network. Moreover, inspite of the continuous modernization of vehicles and road infrastructure considering safety as a major goal, the growing traffic casualties throughout the world is a serious cause of concerns. In Conventional VANET, Due to the significant research and technology advancements in wireless communication, the traditional Intelligent Transport System (ITS) has evolved towards vehicular communication networks. The concept of Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) and Vehicle-to-Roadside unit (V2R) communication came into existence in research and developments as another communication network known as Vehicular Adhoc Networks (VANETs). It enables communication between on-road vehicles with and without the help of any pre-established infrastructure alongside roads or moving on roads. A number of state-of-the-art equipment related to new generation Wireless Access Technology (WAT) are incorporated with vehicles. The equipment include display screen, sensor, antenna, camera, radar, Global Positioning System (GPS) receiver, multiple Application Units (AU), Central Processing Unit (CPU), etc.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

The block diagram explains the principle parts or functions of the system. There are 3 sections here. Firstly we discuss about V2P (Vehicle to person side) and V2S (Vehicle to sensor side). Second section is V2V (vehicle to vehicle side). finally, V2R (Vehicle to road side) and V2I (vehicle to infrastructure).

1. Block diagram of V2P and V2S

2. Block diagram of V2V

3. Block diagram of V2R and V2I

BLOCK DESCRIPTION

A. Microcontroller

The microcontroller that has been used for this project is from pic series. Pic microcontroller is the first risc based microcontroller fabricated in cmos (complimentary metal oxide semiconductor) that uses separate bus for instruction and data allowing simultaneous access of program and data memory. The main advantage of cmos and risc combination is low power consumption resulting in a very small chip size with a small pin count. The main advantage of cmos is that it has immunity to noise than other fabrication techniques. Various microcontrollers offer different kinds of memories. EEPROM, EPROM, FLASH etc. are some of the memories of which FLASH is the most recently developed. Technology that is used in pic16F877 is flash technology, so that data is retained even when the power is switched off. Easy Programming and Erasing are other features of PIC 16F877.

B. Bluetooth Module

Bluetooth wireless technology is becoming a popular standard in the communication arena, and it is one of the fastest growing fields in the wireless communication. It is so convenient, easy to use and has the bandwidth to meet most of today's demands for mobile and personal communications. Bluetooth technology handles the wireless part of the communication channel; It transmits and receives data wirelessly between these devices. It delivers the received data and receives the data to be transmitted to and from a host system through a host controller interface (HCI). The most popular host controller interface today is either a UART or a USB Here only focus on the UART interface, it can be easily show how a Bluetooth module can be integrated on to a host system through a UART connection and provide the designer an optimal solution for Bluetooth enabled systems. Supply voltage at VCC pin can vary between 1.8 V and 3.3 V. VCC and BTEN combined to a single 3.3 V supply voltage.

C. Zigbee Module

Zigbee is the name of a specification for a suite of high level communication protocols by using small, low-power, low data rate digital radios based on the IEEE 802.15.4 standard for wireless personal area networks (WPANs), such as wireless headphones connecting with cell phones via short-range radio. This technology is intended to be simpler and cheaper than other WPANs, such as Bluetooth. Zigbee is targeted at radio-frequency (RF) applications which require a low data rate, long battery life, and secure networking. ZigBee is a low data rate, two-way standard for home automation and data networks. The standard specification for up to 254 nodes including one master, managed from a single remote control. Real usage examples of ZigBee includes home automation tasks such as turning lights on, setting the home security system, or starting the VCR. With ZigBee all these tasks can be done from anywhere in the home at the touch of a button. ZigBee also allows for dial-in access via the Internet for automation control.

D. RF Module

The RF module, as the name suggests, operates at Radio Frequency. The corresponding frequency range varies between 30 kHz & 300 GHz. In this RF system, the digital data is represented as variations in the amplitude of carrier wave. This kind of modulation is known as Amplitude Shift Keying (ASK). Transmission through RF is better than IR (infrared) because of many reasons. Firstly, signals through RF can travel through larger distances making it suitable for long range applications. Also, while IR mostly operates in line-of-sight mode, RF signals can travel even when there is an obstruction between transmitter & receiver. This RF module comprises of an RF Transmitter and an RF Receiver. The transmitter/receiver (Tx/Rx) pair operates at a frequency of 434 MHz. An RF transmitter receives serial data and transmits it wirelessly through RF through its antenna connected at pin4. The transmission occurs at the rate of 1Kbps - 10Kbps. The transmitted data is received by an RF receiver operating at the same frequency as that of the transmitter.

E. Accelerometer

Body in motion usually experience vibration as well as shock. When a mobile falls on a floor, it is subjected to shock. When a vehicle moves on a bumpy road, it experiences vibrations. Likewise, there are many situations, where an object encounters shock and vibrations. Sometimes, they survive and at times, they get damaged. When delicate items like glass, crockery, etc. are packaged properly, they can withstand severe shock and vibrations. Whether a system will survive or not, how do we know this a priori? While some vibrations are desirable, some may be disturbing or even destructive. Hence, often a need is felt to understand the causes of vibrations and to develop methods to measure and prevent them.

F. OBD

OBD stands for on-Board Diagnostics. Most 1996 and newer vehicles have standardized computer system (also known as OBDII) that continually monitor the electronic sensor of engines and emission control systems, including the catalytic converter, while the vehicle is being driven to ensure they are working as designed.

G. GSM Module

A GSM modem is a specialized type of modem which accepts a SIM card, and operates over a subscription to a mobile operator, just like a mobile phone. When a GSM modem is connected to a computer, this allows the computer to use the GSM modem to communicate over the mobile network. While these GSM modems are most frequently used to provide mobile internet connectivity, many of them can also be used for sending and receiving SMS and MMS.

H. Power Supply

A power supply is used for supplying the power to all parts with their specifications. The purpose of power supply here is that because PIC16F877A requires 5 volts, ZigBee requires 3.3 volts. A variable regulated power supply, also called a variable bench power supply, is one where you can continuously adjust the output voltage to your requirements. Varying the output of the power supply is the recommended way to test a project after having double checked parts placement against circuit drawings and the parts placement guide. This type of regulation is ideal for having a simple variable bench power supply.

SIMULATION RESULT

The circuit diagram and programming for overall circuit was drawn in software named proteus design suite and simulated by connecting the program written in keil microvision software using micro c.

The circuit diagram (Circuit diagram of V2P and V2S) represents the vehicle to person side communication and vehicle to sensor side communication. In this section we mainly focus on women security. Now a days, in our society women's are suffering with a lot of mental and physical harassment. In this project, introducing an easiest way for ladies to protect themselves when they are travelling in a call taxi or any other vehicle alone. Here the RF button is the transmission section.

Next, introducing the vehicle to vehicle to vehicle communication system. In which the communication between the vehicles are possible. The person in one vehicle can communicate and contact with the person in the nearest vehicle. So they can help each other in a critical situation.

Circuit diagram of V2P and V2S

Circuit diagram of V2V

Circuit diagram of V2R and V2I

In first section of circuit that is a v2s and v2p communication. v2p communication is working based on the signal from rf transmitter (ear ring button). in transmission side they have a button interfacing with rf module, the button and the rf module is attached in the person side. when person have any trouble in the vehicle she can press the button. that time a data will send through the rf transmitter module. then data will received in the vehicle side unit. in vehicle side unit there is a microcontroller, bluetooth module, android application and rf receiver module. the transmitted data will receive the rf receiver and send to microcontroller then the microcontroller send another data through bluetooth module to android application. android application receive the data through bluetooth network and send message to police station. in v2s communication where using different sensors. The sensors read the values from vehicle and send to microcontroller, the microcontroller store the data in cloud using ZIGBEE network. In V2V communication, it is a vehicle to vehicle communication in this communication sharing vehicle details in to another vehicle using zigbee. In this circuit we using different sensors. These sensors are connected with microcontroller. The microcontroller read the values from sensors. And checking the changes in sensor readings, and also send these data through zigbee in to another vehicle. The last one circuit is road side unit. This circuit also communicate with vehicles through zigbee network. When an accident is accrued the vehicle side unit is pas a data to roadside unit, when receive an alert signal from vehicle the road side unite send message to near side hospitals. And also send these data to cloud.

APPLICATIONS

- The vehicular communications of IoV would be highly commercialized.
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- The network architecture of IoV would integrate vehicular communication with other communication networks. IoV would provide reliable Internet service in vehicles. This is due to the inclusion of V2I communication.
- The processing and decision making capability of vehicles, size of vehicular networks, volume of network data would enlarge drastically in IoV. Accident Prevention
- Car Payment-Unique cyber space identity would enable car payment.
- On-road Internet- The reliable Internet services in vehicles would add new devices in on-line cyberspace in large volume.

CONCLUSION

Internet of Vehicles (IoV) is evolving as a global heterogeneous vehicular networks. The emerging concept of ‘Connected Drive’ in smart transportation is the basis of IoV. The two major objectives of IoV include automation of various security and efficiency features in vehicles and commercialization of vehicular networks. The important factor in IoV is speed. It always communicate with nearby vehicles and other control rooms. The network model is proposed by identifying three network elements of IoV including cloud, connection and client. The challenges and issues ahead in the design and development of IoV are discussed.

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